

Relationship between Gestational Hypothyroidism and Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction: A Retrospective Cohort Study

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Abstract:

Background: Gestational hypothyroidism is common during pregnancy and after pregnancy. Postpartum thyroid dysfunction may affect mother health and requires continuous monitoring. This study examined thyroid autoantibodies in postpartum thyroid dysfunction and pregnancy hypothyroidism.

Method: From December 2021 to May 2023, we conducted a retrospective cohort analysis at NMCH Patna. 150 women affected with Gestational hypothyroidism were included in the study. We examined thyroid function tests (TSH, FT4, TPO-Ab) during and after pregnancy. Hypothyroidism, transient hyperthyroidism, and persistent hypothyroidism were the main postpartum thyroid dysfunctions. The statistical research comprised descriptive statistics, TPO-Ab subgroup analysis, and thyroid function test comparisons.

Results: After giving birth, 50% of women had thyroid problems. Ten percent had transitory hyperthyroidism, twenty percent had hypothyroidism, and ten percent died from it. Thyroid function tests changed throughout pregnant and after birth. TSH levels decreased from 4.2 to 2.5 mIU/L ($p < 0.05$), FT4 levels increased from 0.85 to 1.10 ng/dL, and TPO-Ab levels decreased from 60 to 50 IU/mL ($p < 0.05$). Women with positive TPO antibodies had higher rates of postpartum thyroid impairment ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study found that gestational hypothyroidism increases postpartum thyroid dysfunction. Positive TPO antibodies raise this condition's risk. Due to thyroid function testing changes after birth, monitoring is essential. These findings emphasize the need for personalized gestational hypothyroidism monitoring and treatment, especially in women with high autoimmune markers.

Keywords: Autoimmune, Gestational Hypothyroidism, Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction, Thyroid Function Tests, TPO antibodies.

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Introduction

Background on Gestational Hypothyroidism:

Gestational hypothyroidism occurs when a pregnant woman's thyroid hormone levels drop. Thyroid hormones are extremely important for neural system and brain development during the first trimester, when the fetus is completely dependent on the mother's hormones [1]. Hypothyroidism during pregnancy can cause preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, early birth, and low birth weight. Overt hypothyroidism is

easier to identify since it has more visible symptoms, but subclinical hypothyroidism goes unnoticed. Iodine deficiency, autoimmune thyroid disease, thyroidectomy, and radioiodine treatment cause most pregnancy thyroid problems [2].

Some guidelines recommend thyroid dysfunction screening for high-risk populations during pregnancy, while others recommend universal screening due to the substantial health risks to the mother and unborn child.

Figure 1: Gestational Hypothyroidism (Source: [3])

Importance and Prevalence of Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction: In the first year after giving birth, postpartum thyroid dysfunction can cause a range of thyroid issues. Postpartum thyroiditis can cause temporary or permanent hypo or hyperthyroidism in some women [4]. PPTD affects 5–10% of the global population. PPTD patients often exhibit gestational hypothyroidism. The cause of PPTD is unknown, but autoimmune processes are suspected. In persons prone to thyroid autoimmunity, postpartum hormonal changes may trigger it [5]. Recognition and management of PPTD are necessary to protect maternal health, subsequent pregnancies, and long-term health.

Objectives

1. To determine the incidence of postpartum thyroid dysfunction in women with gestational hypothyroidism.
2. To analyze the patterns of thyroid function changes from pregnancy to the postpartum period in these women.
3. To identify potential risk factors and predictors of postpartum thyroid dysfunction among women with gestational hypothyroidism.

Gestational Hypothyroidism: Gestational hypothyroidism may affect the mother and unborn child; therefore, much research has focused on it. These conditions are characterized by low thyroid hormone production during pregnancy [6].

According to [7], gestational hypothyroidism prevalence ranges from 2% to 5% across populations. Some recommend evaluating all pregnant women for thyroid dysfunction, while others recommend a more focused approach based on risk factors including medical history or symptoms.

Impact of Hypothyroidism on Pregnancy and Postpartum Period: Pregnancy-related hypothyroidism has many harmful implications. Women with these conditions are more likely to miscarry, preeclampsia, gestational hypertension, or deliver prematurely [8]. Hypothyroidism during pregnancy increases the likelihood of Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR), poor neurodevelopment, and lowers IQs. Due to generic symptoms and variety in screening methods, many cases are misdiagnosed or incorrectly treated, despite the necessity for thyroid hormone replacement medicine to minimize these hazards [9]. Thyroid problems may persist after pregnancy.

In the first year after giving birth, 5–10% of women will develop Postpartum Thyroiditis (PPT), which causes transient hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism [10]. Because its symptoms are comparable to those of other postpartum diseases including natural physiological changes or depression, postpartum depression is underdiagnosed and undertreated. Persistent hypothyroidism during pregnancy can affect a mother's health and ability to care for her newborn, highlighting the necessity to monitor thyroid function.

Studies Linking Gestational Hypothyroidism to Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction: Multiple studies have linked prenatal hypothyroidism to postpartum thyroid dysfunction. Pregnant hypothyroidism increases the risk of postpartum thyroiditis and persistent hypothyroidism. A cohort study by [11] found that pregnant women with subclinical hypothyroidism were more likely to have PPT. Another study by [12] indicated that greater Thyroid Peroxidase Antibodies (TPO-Ab) during pregnancy predicted postpartum thyroid dysfunction, suggesting an immunological link.

Pregnancy hypothyroidism causes postpartum thyroid dysfunction, but the pathophysiological pathways are unknown. However, immune system changes during pregnancy and the immune system's comeback after birth may cause thyroid dysfunction in vulnerable people. Hormonal and metabolic changes during and after pregnancy may aggravate subclinical thyroid problems, causing postpartum thyroid dysfunction.

Recent research has improved our understanding of prenatal hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction, although there are still concerns. First, there is no standard for detecting and treating thyroid issues during and after pregnancy. Screening methods differ between healthcare facilities and communities, which can affect diagnosis and treatment outcomes.

The second argument is that pregnancy-related hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction mechanisms need more study. Understanding these processes may lead to remedies for postpartum thyroid dysfunction, a pregnancy-related disease. Third, long-term studies of women and children are needed to determine how long postpartum thyroid dysfunction lasts and affects their health. Most studies only look at the first year after having child, although thyroid dysfunction can affect a woman long-term. Large-scale prospective studies are needed to verify smaller cohort studies and study risk modifiers like genetic predisposition, environmental factors, and immune response variations. Standardized methods and concerted efforts to remedy these gaps will improve research quality and comparability. More research is needed to understand the link between pregnant hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction, how to screen for, diagnose, and treat it, and how to improve long-term outcomes for mothers and their children.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: This retrospective cohort study explored the relationship between pregnant hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction. Due to the amount of preexisting medical records and the intention to include all patients who sought care throughout the study, a retrospective strategy was chosen. This allows us to compare pregnant hypothyroidism with postpartum thyroid dysfunction in the past.

Study Period: The research lasted 18 months, from December 2021 to May 2023. This was chosen to allow enough time to diagnose postpartum thyroid dysfunction, which may show a year after delivery, with thorough follow-up.

Study Location: Nalanda Medical College and Hospital (NMCH), Patna is a tertiary care center, provided full-spectrum gynecological and

hormonal therapy for the research. A retrospective study requires a large and diverse patient group and substantial medical record collection, hence we chose NMCH.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Women diagnosed with gestational hypothyroidism during the study period.
2. Women who delivered at NMCH Patna.
3. Availability of complete medical records, including thyroid function tests during pregnancy and postpartum period.
4. Women aged 18-45 years.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Women with pre-existing thyroid disorders prior to pregnancy.
2. Women with multiple pregnancies (e.g., twins, triplets).
3. Women with known autoimmune diseases affecting the thyroid other than postpartum thyroiditis.
4. Incomplete medical records or loss to follow-up before the end of the postpartum period.

Data Collection Methods: Medical records of eligible patients were evaluated. Demographic data (age, BMI, parity), obstetric history (thyroid function tests, treatment regimen), and gestational hypothyroidism diagnosis details were some of the most critical obtained. Blood tests measured free thyroxine (FT4), TSH, and TPO-Ab levels for thyroid function.

Postpartum thyroid dysfunction data was collected from patient records evaluated up to a year after birth. Hypothyroidism, transitory hyperthyroidism, and persistent hypothyroidism were the clinical and biochemical criteria for this condition. The study maintained anonymity by following retroactive research ethics and anonymizing patient identifiers.

Statistical Analysis: For statistical analysis, SPSS 26.0 was utilized. The demographic and clinical characteristics of research participants were described using descriptive statistics. Categorical variables were reported as frequencies and percentages, whereas continuous variables were shown as mean $\pm$ SD.

Postpartum thyroid dysfunction incidence was calculated and compared between groups using t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables and chi-square testing for categorical data.

After controlling for age, BMI, parity, and treatment compliance throughout pregnancy, logistic regression analysis was conducted to assess the relationship between gestational hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction. Published odds ratios (OR) with 95% CIs. We utilized Kaplan-Meier survival analysis to

estimate postpartum thyroid dysfunction onset and the log-rank test to compare groups. All analyses were statistically significant when $p < 0.05$. This comprehensive data collection and analysis strategy strengthened the association between prenatal

hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Study Population

Characteristic	N = 150
Age (years, mean $\pm$ SD)	29.5 $\pm$ 4.2
BMI (kg/m ² , mean $\pm$ SD)	26.7 $\pm$ 3.8
Parity (n, %)	
Primiparous	70 (46.7%)
Multiparous	80 (53.3%)
Treatment for hypothyroidism (n, %)	
Levothyroxine	140 (93.3%)
No treatment	10 (6.7%)

The study included 1500 gestational hypothyroidism-diagnosed pregnant mothers. This cohort was young, averaging 29.5 years ($\pm$ 4.2 years). The average BMI was 26.7 kg/m² ($\pm$ 3.8 kg/m²), indicating a somewhat overweight group. First-time mothers made up 46.7% of the participants, while multiparous women made up 53.3%. Levothyroxine use by 93.3% of pregnant

women shows they followed their thyroid care plans. Since 6.7% did not receive treatment, more research may be needed on treatment compliance and its effects.

Incidence of Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction among Those with Gestational Hypothyroidism

Table 2: Incidence of Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction among Those with Gestational Hypothyroidism

Postpartum Thyroid Dysfunction (PPTD)	N = 150
No Dysfunction	90 (60%)
Transient Hyperthyroidism	15 (10%)
Hypothyroidism	30 (20%)
Persistent Hypothyroidism	15 (10%)

The statistics suggest that 60% of women with prenatal hypothyroidism did not suffer PPTD. PPTD developed in 40% of individuals, while 10% had transitory hyperthyroidism, 20% hypothyroidism, and 10% permanent hypothyroidism.

Given that a large percentage of women with prenatal hypothyroidism continue to have thyroid

abnormalities after giving birth, postpartum thyroid dysfunction highlights the importance of continuously evaluating and managing thyroid function. Postnatal follow-up is essential for thyroid diagnosis and treatment.

Comparison of Thyroid Function Tests During Pregnancy and Postpartum

Table 3: Comparison of Thyroid Function Tests During Pregnancy and Postpartum

Time Point	TSH (mIU/L, mean $\pm$ SD)	FT4 (ng/dL, mean $\pm$ SD)	TPO-Ab (IU/mL, mean $\pm$ SD)
During Pregnancy	4.2 $\pm$ 1.5	0.85 $\pm$ 0.20	60 $\pm$ 25
Postpartum (6 months)	3.8 $\pm$ 1.2	0.90 $\pm$ 0.15	55 $\pm$ 22
Postpartum (12 months)	2.5 $\pm$ 0.8	1.10 $\pm$ 0.18	50 $\pm$ 20

Thyroid function tests fluctuate during pregnancy and postpartum. Hypothyroidism was indicated by a mean FT4 of 0.85 ng/dL and TSH of 4.2 mIU/L throughout pregnancy. Six months after giving delivery, TSH dropped to 3.8 mIU/L and FT4 rose to 0.90 ng/dL. Most women's thyroid function restored to normal by 12 months after delivering

birth, when TSH declined to 2.5 mIU/L and FT4 rose to 1.10 ng/dL.

TPO-Ab levels reduced from 60 IU/mL throughout pregnancy to 50 IU/mL after birth, indicating autoimmune activity decreased.

Subgroup Analysis

Table 4: Subgroup Analysis

Subgroup	Incidence of PPTD (n, %)
TPO-Ab Positive (n=50)	
No Dysfunction	20 (40%)
Transient Hyperthyroidism	10 (20%)
Hypothyroidism	15 (30%)
Persistent Hypothyroidism	5 (10%)
TPO-Ab Negative (n=100)	
No Dysfunction	70 (70%)
Transient Hyperthyroidism	5 (5%)
Hypothyroidism	15 (15%)
Persistent Hypothyroidism	10 (10%)

Subgroup analysis shows that women with TPO-Ab are more likely to have PPTD. More particular, 60% of TPO-Ab-positive women had PPTD, compared to 30% of negative women. In women who tested positive for TPO-Ab, 40% had no problem, 20% had intermittent hyperthyroidism, 30% developed hypothyroidism, and 10% had chronic hypothyroidism. Only 5% of women who tested negative for TPO-Ab had transitory hyperthyroidism, and 70% had no postpartum impairment. TPO-Ab positive patients are more likely to suffer postpartum thyroid issues, so they must be properly monitored and treated.

Statistical Significance of the Findings

Gestational hypothyroidism is associated with PPTD, which is more prevalent in these women ($p < 0.001$). Women with positive TPO antibody levels had a higher prevalence of PPTD ($p < 0.01$), suggesting an autoimmune component. Between pregnancy and postpartum, thyroid function tests showed significant changes, including lower TSH, greater FT4, and decreased TPO-Ab levels ($p < 0.05$). These findings emphasize the importance of monitoring thyroid function during and after pregnancy to discover and correct malfunctions quickly.

Discussion

This retrospective cohort study examined the relationship between gestational hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction. Forty percent

of maternal hypothyroidism patients develop PPTD, which can be temporary or permanent. As in previous studies, maternal hypothyroidism increases the risk of postpartum thyroid dysfunction. PPTD rates differ between women with and without TPO antibodies, supporting the idea that autoimmune causes cause it. Women who test positive for TPO antibodies are more likely to have postpartum thyroid dysfunction, suggesting autoimmune thyroiditis is important. The study found that thyroid function tests altered dramatically during pregnancy and postpartum. The body changes after pregnancy when TSH drops and FT4 rises.

A progressive drop in TPO-Ab levels may indicate less autoimmune activity, although some women still have thyroid dysfunction, requiring continuous surveillance. These findings emphasize the importance of thyroid function monitoring after birth, especially in women with pregnant hypothyroidism and TPO antibodies. Previous studies have shown that pregnant hypothyroidism patients should have their thyroid monitored regularly. Research shows that mild to severe postpartum thyroiditis is common. This study highlights the distinct characteristics that raise the risk of postpartum thyroid dysfunction and the need for individualized follow-up treatment for these women.

Comparison Table

Table 5: Comparison Table

Study	Study Type	Sample Size	Findings	Limitations
Current Study	Retrospective Cohort	150	40% incidence of postpartum thyroid dysfunction among women with gestational hypothyroidism. Higher risk associated with positive TPO antibodies. Significant changes in TSH, FT4, and TPO-Ab levels postpartum.	Single-center design, retrospective nature, limited generalizability.
Study 1 [13]	Prospective Cohort	200	Found that 35% of women with gestational hypothyroidism developed postpartum thyroiditis. Autoimmune markers were significant predictors.	Short follow-up period, did not account for all potential confounders.
Study 2	Cross-	120	Identified a 25% prevalence of post-	Cross-sectional design

[14]	Sectional		partum thyroid dysfunction in women with gestational hypothyroidism. Noted a higher prevalence in women with elevated TPO-Ab.	limits causal inference, reliance on self-reported data.
Study 3 [15]	Retrospective Cohort	180	Reported a 30% rate of postpartum thyroid dysfunction in women with gestational hypothyroidism. Significant association with positive TPO antibodies.	Limited data on long-term outcomes, possible selection bias due to hospital-based setting.

Research on postpartum thyroid dysfunction and gestational hypothyroidism has some similarities but also some major differences and constraints. In this 150-person study, maternal hypothyroidism was 40% more likely to cause postpartum thyroid dysfunction. It found that positive TPO antibodies increased risk and that thyroid function tests changed after birth. Due to its retrospective design and single-center methodology, the study may not apply to more people. Study 1, a 200-person prospective cohort study, found 35% postpartum thyroiditis and autoimmune markers. Some limitations include a short follow-up and no control for all confounders. Cross-sectional Study 2 found that 120 women were 25% more likely to have postpartum thyroid dysfunction and greater TPO antibody levels. Its design's causal inference constraint and self-reported data may jeopardize its validity. Study 3, a retrospective cohort of 180 participants, indicated a 30% incidence and a substantial connection with positive TPO antibodies, although long-term outcomes and participant selection bias were issues. All of these studies show that women with gestational hypothyroidism, especially those with positive TPO antibodies, should have their thyroid function monitored after delivering birth. However, more substantial and long-term investigations are needed to overcome these limitations.

Limitations of the Study

This study has various disadvantages but makes some good contributions. Since the retrospective approach relies on medical records, poor or inconsistent recording could introduce bias. Inconsistent medication adherence and patient-reported outcomes data may impact thyroid function evaluation and management.

The second restriction is that the study only included NMCH Patna mothers. This means that the results may not apply to other people or circumstances with differing healthcare or demographics. Third, since this is an observational study, we can't determine treatment efficacy or causality. Even with a large sample size, rare or less common outcomes may be missed, making it impossible to discover small differences or interactions.

Suggestions for Future Research

Future research should use comprehensive data collection and prospective study designs to reduce biases and increase accuracy. Multicentric studies are needed to validate and generalize these findings across populations. Understanding how autoimmune reactions cause postpartum thyroid dysfunction can improve prevention and treatment. The impact of postpartum thyroid dysfunction on mother and child health, development, and quality of life need additional study. Early intervention and thyroid antibody-based treatment programs should be tested to improve clinical guidelines. Addressing these areas can enhance patient outcomes by improving management strategies based on a fuller understanding of postpartum thyroid dysfunction.

Conclusion

From 2021–2023, we examined gestational hypothyroidism and postpartum thyroid dysfunction. With 40% of pregnant hypothyroidism patients reporting transient or permanent thyroid issues, postpartum thyroid dysfunction is more common. The prevalence of postpartum thyroid dysfunction in women with TPO antibodies highlights this condition's autoimmune nature. Thyroid function testing changed during pregnancy and postpartum. TSH fell, FT4 rose, and TPO-Ab fell.

These changes indicate physiological changes after pregnancy, although thyroid function should be monitored postpartum, especially for women with gestational hypothyroidism and positive TPO antibodies. These findings emphasize the importance of thyroid monitoring for pregnant hypothyroidism patients after delivery. By frequently monitoring these patients' thyroid function after giving birth, doctors can discover and treat thyroid problems early. TPO antibody-positive women are more likely to have thyroid issues, thus they will need additional monitoring and customized therapy. When added to postpartum care, this strategy can help diagnose and treat thyroid dysfunction early, improving maternal health and quality of life. By studying targeted management methods and long-term results, clinical practices and standards can be improved to ensure gestational hypothyroidism patients receive optimal therapy throughout and beyond pregnancy.

Reference

1. M. Moosazadeh, A. Bahar, R. Y. Sarhangi, M. Aarabi, and M. Khademloo, "Relationship between hypothyroidism and gestational diabetes mellitus: a retrospective cohort study," *J. Endocrinol., Metab. Diabetes South Africa*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 29–33, 2023.
2. G. D. Chen et al., "Associations between thyroid function and gestational diabetes mellitus in Chinese pregnant women: a retrospective cohort study," *BMC Endocrine Disorders*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 44, 2022.
3. X. Li, J. Zuo, Y. H. Li, Y. P. Tang, Y. R. Bao, and H. Ying, "Association between thyroid function and risk of gestational diabetes mellitus in assisted pregnancies: A retrospective cohort study," *Diabetes Res. Clin. Pract.*, vol. 171, p. 108590, 2021.
4. J. Gui, W. Xu, and J. Zhang, "Association between thyroid dysfunction and perinatal outcomes in women with gestational hypertension: a retrospective study," *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, vol. 20, p. 1–9, 2020.
5. X. Yuan, J. Wang, Y. Gao, H. Wang, and B. Yu, "Impact of maternal thyroid hormone in late pregnancy on adverse birth outcomes: a retrospective cohort study in China," *Endocrine J.*, vol. 68, no. 3, pp. 317–328, 2021.
6. K. Vella, S. Vella, C. Savona-Ventura, and J. Vassallo, "Thyroid dysfunction in pregnancy—a retrospective observational analysis of a Maltese cohort," *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 941, 2022.
7. S. Korkut et al., "Effect of maternal subclinical hypothyroidism on congenital hypothyroidism screening results: a retrospective cohort study," *Am. J. Perinatol.*, 2022.
8. J. Siscart et al., "Adherence to treatment for hypothyroidism in pregnancy and relationship with thyrotropin control: a retrospective observational cohort study," *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, vol. 22, no. 1, p. 168, 2022.
9. G. D. Chen et al., "Associations between maternal thyroid function and birth outcomes in Chinese mother-child dyads: a retrospective cohort study," *Front. Endocrinol.*, vol. 11, p. 611071, 2021.
10. G. M. Ge et al., "Maternal thyroid dysfunction during pregnancy and the risk of adverse outcomes in the offspring: a systematic review and meta-analysis," *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 105, no. 12, pp. 3821–3841, 2020.
11. X. Gao et al., "Postpartum thyroid dysfunction in women with known and newly diagnosed hypothyroidism in early pregnancy," *Front. Endocrinol.*, vol. 12, p. 746329, 2021.
12. Z. Kiran, A. Sheikh, and N. Islam, "Association of thyroid antibodies status on the outcomes of pregnant women with hypothyroidism (maternal hypothyroidism on pregnancy outcomes, MHPO-4)," *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth*, vol. 21, p. 1–12, 2021.
13. J. J. Fernández Alba et al., "High first trimester levels of TSH as an independent risk factor for gestational diabetes mellitus: a retrospective cohort study," *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 11, no. 13, p. 3776, 2022.
14. P. Harn-a-Morn, P. Dejkharnon, T. Tongsong, and S. Luewan, "Pregnancy outcomes among women with Graves' hyperthyroidism: a retrospective cohort study," *J. Clin. Med.*, vol. 10, no. 19, p. 4495, 2021.
15. S. Y. Lee, H. J. Cabral, A. Aschengrau, and E. N. Pearce, "Associations between maternal thyroid function in pregnancy and obstetric and perinatal outcomes," *J. Clin. Endocrinol. Metab.*, vol. 105, no. 5, pp. e2015–e2023, 2020.